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E-LEARNING IN GLOBAL EDUCATION: CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS.

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Abstract

Globalization is a phenomenon that represents the emerging worldwide interdependence of individuals and countries, which is characterized by various economic, political, cultural and social relatives (Anyakoha, 2006). A typical example of this multidimensional concept is the Information and Communication Technology (ICT), which has created new global networks, dismantling national boundaries and barriers, thereby generating a global village where one can access information from any part of the universe within seconds. The present paper discussed e-learning as an initiative of globalization. The major challenges of e-learning as an innovation in enhancing the creation and transfer of information in a global arena as well as the prospects of e-learning, were addressed. The paper concluded with recommendation on how to address the identified challenges.

E-learning is construed in a variety of contexts, some as distance learning, others as online learning; yet others as network learning (Wilson, 2001). Volery (2000) argued that the fast expansion of the internet, and related technological advancement, in conjunction with limited budgets and social demands for improved access to higher education, has produced a substantial incentive for universities to introduce e-learning courses. Volery (2000) went further to say that universities must embrace e-learning technology that is readily available or they will be left behind in the pursuit for globalization.

However, Ribiero (2002) posited that the utilization of ICT, with its attendant success story, is not without financial sacrifices, which are recurrent in nature. Stutzke (2000) confirmed this assertion when he stated that the life span of software engineering is less than three years. This gives an insight as to how dynamic software development and, indeed, ICT is.

O'Hearn (2000), contended that university structures are rigid and unproven, regarding the incorporation of technological advancements.

These assertions are common place in Nigeria and Nigerian Universities. University of Calabar, for instance, is just introducing the marking of Post UTME examination using computer, a variant of ICT. The process is still at its rudimentary state such that the computers failed so many students that management had to revisit the marking of the said examination. As if that is not enough, the website of the university is full of online admission errors such that it would not be tolerated in another discipline.

Cuban (2000) observed that computers had limitations such as frequent breakdown, very short lifespan (frequent change of models or technology) and difficult to use. The bandwidth in cyber café is dead slow; the Internet is down most of the time for various reasons including power failures and outages.

Bearing in mind that the educational system of the society can not grow above the level of the teacher who implements it, Holley (2000) stated that e-learning is difficult to implement without the full cooperation and support of lecturers (teachers). The political stability and fruitful legislative decisions can bring about a great change to e-learning in Nigeria.

For instance, in 1995, for the first time a presidential panel on educational technology was commissioned to advise the President of America on how computer technology, and hence e-learning could be used to strengthen the primary and post primary education in the country (Panel of Educational Technology, 1997). This panel concluded that the amount of computing and networking equipment available for instruction in schools remained "sub-optimum" and a large share was "obsolete and of very limited utility". More importantly, the report also argued that the problem was not just in the infrastructure but in the lack of adequate staff preparation and support.

In Nigeria, the Obasanjo regime (1999-2007) instituted many political policies:

The National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) was born, to mop up the teeming Nigerians who are yearning for University education, but could not be absorbed by conventional universities, especially the working populace. The one laptop per child (OLPC) was also introduced to Nigerian government by its founder, Professor Nicholas Negroponte. During this same period, Internet Penetration in Nigeria rose by three percent (3%), above the less than one percent (<1%) in early 2000 (IT & Technology Digest, 2008).

In April 2001, National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) was established to foster the development and growth of ICT in Nigeria.

Nigerian Universities approach to e-learning is still at the infant state. Very many Universities produce graduates who can not use the computer and the internet, per se, the introduction of GSS 2111 and 2112 (Computer Literacy Program) for Undergraduate students notwithstanding. It is sad to state here that even computer science majors are not employable in the current ICT firms. Industries are very far ahead of the university system, and as such would require graduates of Nigerian Universities to be ICT certified in various fields like MCSE (Microsoft Certified Software Engineer), Cisco Certified Network Associate (CCNA), to mention but a few. Jones (2000) confirmed this sad situation by warning that if traditional institutions are to remain dominant education providers and advance technically, they must embrace the knowledge and experience of external clients (the industry) in the latest distance learning revolution. However, Dobbs (2000) rose to the defense of Nigerian Universities when he stated that while traditional higher education institutions endeavor to learn more about implementing e-learning from external organizations, they are extremely cautious with regard to connecting themselves to potentially precarious organizations.

E-learning has come to stay because it seems to be the saving grace for educationally hungry Nigerians who could not be absorbed by conventional universities, who are already working and would want to improve their knowledge, etc.

E-LEARNING INITIATIVES AND GLOBAL EDUCATION; APPROACHES

It is almost impossible to talk about globalization without e-learning. Global education has come to be construed as borderless education; education made possible by ICT (Njoku, 2006). Globalization has unified the entire world into one small village with common socio-economic, political, cultural and educational systems and we now talk of the World Economic Order, World Educational System etc. Therefore, educational systems and nations that still think they are "islands", according to Njoku (2006) merely deceive themselves.

Globalization as a call to duty, urges us to modernize our various processes with large scale technological innovation. Efemini (2000) saw the educational sector as one sector that needs this radical change most, because it is capable of guaranteeing the creation and transfer of information to be used in this age.

In the ICT era, every conceivable activity has gone virtual and the trend now is encouragement of e-learning in all fields of learning (Durosaro, 2010). Durosaro noted that in modern times, we have teleconferences, workshops and seminars in which teachers can participate to broaden their knowledge and outlook and through online education, the nation may even be able to balance the demand and supply of teachers across the states of Nigeria.

The need for the development of ICT for learning is a global resolution and has been a subject of great significance to all mankind. Consequently, upon her recognition of the seriousness of ICT, Nigeria in 2001 formulated the Nigerian National policy for Information Technology (NNPIT) with the objective of using ICT as not only for education but also to create wealth, eradicate poverty, create jobs and as an engine for sustainable development and global competitiveness (National Information Technology Development Agency, 2003). In strong support of the National Information and Telecommunication vision and on the basis of the self-evident indispensability of ICT in the teaching-learning process, the relevant authorities have made the acquisition of basic ICT skills and

capabilities part of the National Minimum Standards for Teacher Education at both the Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) and first degrees in Education. These guidelines are clearly contained in the National Minimum Standards issued by the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE), the National Universities Commission (NUC), and the Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN).

In progressive nations, the classroom is simply an integration of ICT with virtually every teacher having a computer and at most two students sharing a computer right there in the classroom. Formative and summative e-assessments have equally become common in these nations, (Atkinson and Davis, 2011).

There is therefore no gain-saying that effective e-learning comes from using information and communication technology (ICT) to broaden educational opportunity and help students develop skills needed to compete in the global market. The question now is, in the face of the available technology, is the Nigerian teacher/learner government and the society ready for effective e-learning that will plunge the nation properly in the arena of globalization? Which proactive approach can be followed to make e-learning a reality in Nigeria?

In attempting to provide answers to these questions, it is important to know that both the teacher and the students are in this race. It is also very appalling to note that the race has become rather dramatic as students through their increased interest and experiences in on-line activities seem to be leading the teachers, parents and other stakeholders in e-capabilities. Besides, the most important agencies: JAMB, NECO, WAEC dealing with students have all gone on-line, and students getting deeper and deeper in the opportunities presented by the web, the race might not likely end in the teachers' favor except the latter sit up and develop interest in ICT skills. It is important to know that we have come to an era where teachers are no longer the all-knowing but must try by all means not to be totally beaten and forsaken. It is on this basis that Ubaru (2000), pointed to the change in new school paradigm as depicted in the table below:

From	To
School building	Knowledge infrastructure (schools, laboratories, radio, TV, internet resources, etc).
Classrooms	Individual learners
Teacher as provider of knowledge.	Teacher as tutor or facilitator.
A set of text books and few audio/visual aids.	Multimedia materials (print, audio, video, etc).

Challenges

Time required to develop and maintain an e-learning course. Faculty spend substantial time and effort reengineering the course to adapt it for online delivery. This represents a significant amount of added effort for instructions.

Instructors need technical and pedagogical training.

Additional time is needed to communicate with students, especially time to read students' e-mail and respond accordingly.

Technical limitations of course management software. Also the support staff should be versatile in the use of the software. It will be worst if the technical staff lack the technical expertise.

Technological proficiency on the part of teachers.

Lack of back-up materials such as DVD writers, High capacity Hard Disks and Commensurate CPU Speed.

The internet down time and frequency.

Prospect

Course adaptation path: Adaptation requires common sense judgments as to how to take standard classroom practices and plug them into the established e-learning structure.

Self-motivation: No body teaches you to learn. Students motivate themselves intrinsically to learn the technological use of ICT in order to flow in the course. In Nigeria, some NOUN students take private courses on computer literacy to enable them confidently write the online exams.

Computer supported collaborative learning (CSCL): This is a promising innovation to improving teaching and learning with the help of modern information and communications technology (ICT).

Technology Enhanced learning (TEL): This has the goal to improve socio-technical innovations and improving

efficiency and cost effectiveness for e-learning practices, regarding individuals and organizations, independent of time, space and pace.

Technology issues: Online Support Services: With online support services, students get advised by their counselors, registration can be done even when a student is not on campus.

Conclusion

One of the challenges of globalization is that the 21st century would be a knowledge-driven world. This is why the last decade has witnessed a phenomenal growth in the demand for higher education which has not been adequately met by the higher institutions in the country. E-learning innovation could be a means of enhancing and extending the educational experiences of many Nigerian learners through the medium of ICT, sufficient to position the nation for sustainable development and global competitiveness.

Recommendation

The following have been suggested as a way forward in achieving effective e-learning particularly of the distance learning in Nigeria:

Employ the right people to handle e-learning. A large number of ICT professionals are being trained in NIIT, Afrihub, APTECH, SOFTNET. The right facilitator should be engaged.

Adopt gradual digital train-the-trainer (trainer update) program in order to retain the instructors. Internet accessibility is a major problem in all e-learning departments in institutions of higher learning. Internet access should be made available to the students who are disenfranchised for paying to download their study materials after paying for them.

From the Nigerian context, we recommend that NOUN should provide office blocks for her staff in the states and at least one study centre in each local government area headquarters as provided in the handbook. Adequate supply of course and support materials should be made too. This will provide a highly accessible reach that transcends all boundaries.

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